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ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND BUSINESS MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

Abdukhaliqova Komila Abdukhaliqovna

Assistant of the «Marketing» department of the Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Email: komilaa21@gmail.com

Abstract. This article emphasizes the need for rapid reform of the economy in the context of globalization, as well as the role of Uzbekistan as an independent state on the world map. At the same time, the implementation of significant work on the formation of a free economy based on a market economy and the achievement of significant results have been studied as a topical issue. In particular, the growth rates of production, the development of infrastructure and its impact on the development of the economy have been studied.

Key words: entrepreneurship, business, market economy, income, profit, Land, hectare, production, risk.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada globallashuv sharoitida iqtisodiyotni jadal isloh qilish zarurligi, shuningdek, O'zbekistonning mustaqil davlat sifatida jahon xaritasida tutgan o'rni ta'kidlangan. Shu bilan birga, bozor iqtisodiyotiga asoslangan erkin iqtisodiyotni shakllantirish bo'yicha salmoqli ishlarni amalga oshirish va salmoqli natijalarga erishish dolzarb masala sifatida o'rganildi. Xususan, ishlab chiqarishning o'sish sur'atlari, infratuzilmaning rivojlanishi va uning iqtisodiyot rivojiga ta'siri o'rganildi.

Kalit so'zlar: tadbirkorlik, biznes, bozor iqtisodiyoti, daromad, foyda, yer, gektar, ishlab chiqarish, risk.

Аннотация. В данной статье подчеркивается необходимость ускоренного реформирования экономики в условиях глобализации, а также роль Узбекистана как независимого государства на карте мира. При этом рассматривается актуальная проблема реализации значительной работы по формированию свободной экономики на основе рыночной экономики и достижения значительных результатов. В частности, исследуются темпы роста производства, развитие инфраструктуры и её влияние на развитие экономики.

Ключевые слова: предпринимательство, бизнес, рыночная экономика, доход, прибыль, земля, гектар, производство, риск.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of global economic integration, Uzbekistan is confidently pursuing a path of deep reform, modernization, and sustainable development. Over the past three decades, since achieving independence, the country has transitioned from a centrally planned system to a dynamically evolving market economy that prioritizes both private initiative and social welfare. This process has been accompanied by large-scale transformations in institutional structures, legal frameworks, and economic governance mechanisms aimed at ensuring competitiveness, transparency, and inclusiveness.

The government's consistent efforts to liberalize markets, protect private property, and stimulate entrepreneurship have created a solid foundation for the growth of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which today form the backbone of the national economy. At the same time, the adoption of the "Strategy of New Uzbekistan 2022–2026" and the long-term vision "Uzbekistan–2030" have set clear priorities for developing a favorable business environment, introducing digital technologies, and strengthening innovation-driven industries.

In this evolving economic landscape, entrepreneurship and business management have become key drivers of structural modernization and regional diversification. The expanding role of private capital, the integration of modern management practices, and the growing global interconnectedness of local enterprises reflect the country's ambition to establish a competitive, knowledge-based economy. Thus, analyzing the current trends, challenges, and opportunities in entrepreneurship and business management in Uzbekistan is crucial for understanding the trajectory of national economic transformation and its alignment with global best practices.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Entrepreneurship and business are very complex process, and such research has been written by many scientists in their scientific works. Entrepreneurship and business had been studied by Mirziyoyev Sh.M. [1], [2], [3], Mc Connell, Brue [4], N. Gregory Mankiw [5], Y.Shumpeter [6], Xodiev B.Yu., Qosimova M.S., Samadov A.N. [7], Samadov A.N., Ostanaqulova G.N. [8] and Sultonov Sh.A. [9].

Research methodology

In this research, we used of methods of grouping, comparative and structural analysis, induction and deduction, analysis and synthesis, and monographic observations.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

As a result of the consistent implementation of the program of socio-economic development of our country, high, stable and balanced rates of economic growth and trends in macroeconomic stability are strengthening, and living standards are rising.

At the same time, a well-developed development strategy, clear and accurate indication of the goals and objectives of socio-economic reforms, ways to implement them are a solid basis.

Concepts, articles and literature on entrepreneurship and business in Uzbekistan appeared in the mid-60s of the last century. Private property was completely foreign to our politics and ideology at that time.

The concept of entrepreneurship in the modern sense was first used by the English economist Richard Cantillon in the late seventeenth and early eighteenth centuries. In his opinion, an entrepreneur is a person who operates in a risky environment. He therefore saw the land and the labor factor as the source of wealth that determined economic prosperity. Later, in the late eighteenth and early nineteenth centuries, the famous French economist J.B. Sey (1767-1832) in his book "Political Economy" (1803) described the three classical factors of entrepreneurial production - land, capital, labor integrity.

He had argued that the success of British industry was ensured by the 'talent of British entrepreneurs'. J.B. Sey's main thesis is that entrepreneurs play a key role in the production of products. According to J.B. Say, the income received by the entrepreneur is a reward for his labor, organization of production, timely sale of products. The entrepreneur takes the risk and undertakes to produce any product.

It should be noted that the founders of economics paid little attention to the form of entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurial activity was not the object of analysis of their research work. British economists A. Smith (1723-1790) and D. Ricardo (1772-1823) accepted economics as a self-coordinating mechanism. There was no place for creative entrepreneurship in this mechanism. In his book "Study of the nature and causes of the wealth of nations" (1776), A. Smith paid special attention to the definition of entrepreneur. According to A. Smith, the entrepreneur is the owner of capital. He implements a certain commercial idea and starts working with risk in order to make a profit, because spending capital on any business is always associated with risk. Earnings from entrepreneurship, according to A. Smith, are a reward for personal risk. Entrepreneur plans, organizes production, owns the results of production activities. This work, in turn, is related to the market system. That is why A. Smith introduces us to the central mechanism of the market system - the mechanism of competition.

The famous American economist Y. Schumpeter (1883-1950) described the entrepreneur as an innovator in his book The Theory of Economic Development [1]. The scientist believes that entrepreneurial activity is the introduction of innovations that play a major role in the development of the capitalist economy, ensuring economic growth: "We call economic entities whose function is to introduce new combinations."

An Entrepreneurship and business in Uzbekistan began to enter the years of independence, ie in the early 90s, as a science, as a science, its implementation.

World owner Amir Temur in his time paid great attention to entrepreneurship. In his teachings, he said, "A man of business, courage, and determination, a man of determination, determination, entrepreneurship, and vigilance, is better than thousands of careless, indifferent people."

An Entrepreneurship is an economic activity inherent in a market economy. In other words, it is the conscious and purposeful economic activity of the owners or their representatives to organize the production and exchange of goods and services in order to achieve a socio-economic result.

The effective operation and development of small businesses in the Republic of Uzbekistan largely depends on the conditions created for them. Among the conditions that create favorable conditions for the development of small business, it is necessary to highlight infrastructure services.

The word "infrastructure" translates from Latin as "outside the structure." From an economic point of view, the following explanation is more appropriate to the essence of infrastructure: "a specific set of labor processes in the creation of goods and services that provide the exchange of activities in the process of human life and social production."

In recent years, the infrastructure has been developing rapidly. This can be explained by a number of factors. In particular, the growth rate of production is ahead of the development of infrastructure, which also affects the development of the economy.

Infrastructure is a very broad concept, which is primarily related to the creation of service types that provide comprehensive services to the production process.

A small business will benefit greatly from the development of infrastructure units, as such units will free them from the work associated with the provision of production services and allow them to focus their efforts on their core business.

The conditions created by the infrastructure can be categorized as follows:

- Direct production process service - logistics and sales of finished products, information collection and processing, accounting services. Technological, management consulting services and gardens;
- Conditions for the reproduction of the labor force - to support the health, education and training of workers and employees, recreation.

Until now, infrastructure has been considered to be a combination of production and social infrastructure.

There is no doubt that the competitiveness of the national economy also depends on the high share of small business in the indicators that reflect the processes of economic activity and its results.

The word "business" is an English word that means entrepreneurial activity, or in other words, entrepreneurial activity in which people seek to make a profit.

Business means first of all the organization of production, economic activity and relations, and then making money.

An example of the activity of several people in Bulungur district of Samarkand region in the introduction of entrepreneurship and business: Shukhrat Rajabov of H.Olimjon agro-firm first opened a farm on 5 hectares. Then 200 mln. He bought a tractor, a cart and a truck for the farm. She then expanded the farm, first expanding her husband to 10 acres and then to 40 acres

The bank issued 2 billion soums in 2015. and brought 100 heads of cows from Poland. He currently raises 300 head of cattle on the livestock farm. At present, the company has created 50 jobs. During the past 2018-2019, the construction of the floor was carried out landscaping.

Another 2 hectares of unused land were used for supermarkets, teahouses, bakeries, barbershops, shoemakers, kindergartens and other public places. In the past 2019, the company's net profit was 500 million soums.

For example is the entrepreneurial activity of Shavkat Ochilov in Bulungur district: Initially, Sh. Ochilov started a small shop at the entrance to entrepreneurship and business. He then expanded the small shop into a mini-market store.

In 2019, the entrepreneur appealed to the governor of Bulungur district, took 10 hectares of land and established a farm. 500 mln. He bought various equipment, tractors, trucks and livestock for the enterprise. Expanded the enterprise and in 2015 built 2 supermarkets. He took 0.5 hectares of unused land and built a building materials supermarket. Next to the supermarket, he set up a kitchen, a barber shop, a shoemaker's shop, a sewing workshop, a radio workshop and a number of other public service outlets.

As a result, 30 new jobs were created. According to the results of 2019, the net income of the enterprise Sh. Ochilov amounted to 800 million soums. If everyone is enterprising, courageous and courageous, determined, enterprising and vigilant, if he works with the eyes of every business, he will be able to enter the business successfully and achieve great success in this field.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

To get into entrepreneurship and business, people need to deeply explore their internal and external capabilities. It is necessary to pay attention to the following:

1. Has knowledge and skills in the field of entrepreneurship and business;
2. Own personal funds and property;
3. His family supports his plan to start a business.
4. Possibilities to lend to friends and close relatives for a certain period of time;
5. Availability of vacant land for the enterprise he intends to open;
6. Availability of manpower in the area to work in the enterprise;
7. Availability of vehicles and road to the enterprise.

In the case of the above possibilities, the entrepreneur is required to pay attention to the following.

1. Demand for goods produced by the enterprise in the markets;
2. Develop a business and marketing plan;

3. Presence of enterprises producing such products in the vicinity of the place of location of the enterprise, their production, financial, trade situation in the markets;

4. The presence of customers for the products they produce is their demand for the quality and price of goods.

When organizing the work of an entrepreneur it is necessary to do the following:

1. Determine the number and quality of employees working in their company and conduct a competition;

2. Determining ways of remuneration and incentives for employees;

3. Convenience of the location of the enterprise to customers;

4. Whether the location of the enterprise can be expanded;

5. The owner of the enterprise calculates what equipment, raw materials and supplies the entrepreneur needs, how much they cost.

The Entrepreneur is required to set up a perfect accounting system when starting a business:

1. Entrepreneur is required to have knowledge and experience in accounting, banking, obtaining a targeted loan from the bank, its timely repayment and in-depth analysis of other financial processes;

2. Develop a business plan and adhere to it;

3. Entrepreneur to study the advanced technologies of developed countries and introduce them into production;

4. To work tirelessly for the export of manufactured goods to foreign countries.

Many people who want to become an entrepreneur think that starting their own business is a better way than buying an existing business. This approach brings great success and victories to entrepreneurs. It turns, leads to higher risks and, as a result, greater profits and profits.

List of used literature:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. "We will build together a free and prosperous democratic state of Uzbekistan." Speech at the joint session of the Oliy Majlis chambers dedicated to the inauguration ceremony of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan / Sh. Mirziyoyev. // T.: Uzbekistan, 2016.-56 p.
2. Mirziyoyev Sh. M. Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be the daily rule of every leader's activity. Speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan at the meeting of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the results of 2016 and prospects for 2017. // T.: People's word newspaper, January 16, 2017, №11.
3. Mirziyoyev Sh. M. "The rule of law and ensuring the interests of man is a guarantee of the country's development and the well-being of the people." Speech at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the 24th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. // T.: 2016.
4. Mc Connell, Brue. Economics. 17 th edition. // Mcgraw-hill / Irwin, USA, 2014.
5. N. Gregory Mankiw. Principles of Economics, 7 th edition. // Amazon, USA, 2016.
6. Shumpeter J. Theory of economic development. // M.: 1982.
7. Xodiev B.Yu., Qosimova M.S., Samadov A.N. Small business and private entrepreneurship. // T.: TDIU, 2010.
8. Samadov A.N., Ostanaqulova G.N. Small business and entrepreneurship. // T.: Finance and Economics, 2008.
9. Sultonov Sh.A. Small business and entrepreneurship: regional problems and solutions. // S.: - Monograph, SamIES, 2013.

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El.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

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